

EFFECTIVE WAYS TO DEVELOP INTERNATIONAL FRIENDSHIP RELATIONS IN FAMILIES

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Abstract. *The article highlights the issues of preserving language, customs, traditions and culture, unique values, further development of interethnic relations of more than 130 nations and peoples living in multinational Uzbekistan during the years of independence. The reasons for the arrival of people of other nationalities in Uzbekistan, the hospitality and tolerance of the Uzbek people are revealed. The article also notes that equal conditions have been created in Uzbekistan to preserve the national identity of nationalities - for this, 138 national cultural centers operate in the country, coordinated and controlled by a state organization - the International National Center, classes in the republic's schools are conducted in 8 languages. All this is explained by the fact that in Uzbekistan there is mutual understanding in interethnic relations, all nations and peoples living in the republic live in peace and harmony on the basis of the idea “Uzbekistan is our common home”.*

Keywords: *state policy in the field of interethnic relations, concept, migration, ethnic group, interethnic tolerance, interethnic accord, international national center, national cultural centers, national identity.*

Since the first days of independence, one of the priorities of the state policy in Uzbekistan has been the creation of the most favorable conditions for the restoration and preservation of traditional cultural heritage for all nationalities and peoples living in the republic. And this is understandable, because hospitality, kindness, generosity of heart and true tolerance have always been characteristic of our people and have become the basis of its mentality. In the strategy of action on the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, it is emphasized: the peace and tranquility prevailing in our country, friendship and unity, mutual respect and inter-ethnic harmony are the main priceless wealth and independence. is an achievement. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev dated on May 19, 2017 “On measures to further improve international relations and friendly relations with foreign countries” was an important step in this regard.

As noted in the decree, one of the most important priorities of Uzbekistan's state policy is the development of a culture of tolerance and humanity, strengthening inter-ethnic, inter-religious and civil harmony in society, as well as friendly, equal and mutually beneficial relations with foreign countries. is to strengthen relations.

After the independence of Uzbekistan, special attention was paid not only to the local population - the Uzbek people, but also to the creation of equal conditions and opportunities for representatives of different nationalities, and to the preservation of their languages by the ethnic groups living in the republic, as a nation. cultures, values and traditions. The country's leadership has taken steps to resolve the issue by law. In this regard, our country, first of all, arose from the requirements of the Constitution. The attention of all sections of the population and representatives of different nationalities is aimed at ensuring peace, tranquility and international peace, strengthening the most important value facing the country - independence. Equality before the law

was ensured. It was strengthened that in the heart of every citizen there is a sense of responsibility for a single land, a single Motherland that serves the idea of “Uzbekistan is our common home”. Article 4 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that “The Republic of Uzbekistan respects the languages, customs and traditions of all nations and creates conditions for the peoples living in its territory and their development”. Article 8 “People of Uzbekistan are citizens of the independent nation of the Republic of Uzbekistan”. This norm defines the concept of “People of Uzbekistan”. Everyone born, regardless of nationality, race or nationality, lives and works in Uzbekistan, religion, is an equal citizen of our country. Citizens of Uzbekistan, their origin, race, social origin and other circumstances constitute the people of Uzbekistan. “In the Republic of Uzbekistan, all citizens have the same rights and freedoms, regardless of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personal and social status”.

The principle of national equality is strengthened in these articles. The people of Uzbekistan fully comply with the requirements of all international treaties on human rights, including the Paris Charter for a new Europe to which the Republic has joined. It is known from the world experience of Uzbekistan that in multinational countries protection of the rights and freedoms of its citizens, national and cultural interests is one of the most important directions of the same state policy. This requires the creation of necessary conditions for the peoples living outside their historical homeland, able to satisfy their national needs.

This requirement is especially important for peoples who do not have a national territorial structure. National policy during the time of the Soviet government was one-sided. The national question was not resolved in any of the allied republics. Such a policy had a negative impact on the socio-economic development of the Union republics, including Uzbekistan.

Improvement of the mechanisms for the development of interethnic friendly relations in the neighborhoods;

- development of theoretical and methodological bases of sociological research of inter-ethnic friendly relations in neighborhoods; - to determine the state of sociological study of the problem of developing friendships in neighborhoods;

- to reveal the socio-spiritual and political significance of the development of inter-ethnic friendly relations in the country’s development;

- to study the social, economic and spiritual foundations of the development of inter-ethnic friendly relations in the neighborhoods based on the study of public opinion; - Development of interethnic friendly relations in new Uzbekistan

- researching the role and importance of the priority direction of national development;
- based on the sociological study of the role of national-cultural centers in the development of inter-ethnic friendly relations, it consists in developing suggestions and recommendations for improving the processes of inter-ethnic friendly relations development. Further development of interethnic friendly relations in neighborhoods, improvement of mechanisms of cooperation of local executive authorities with institutions of civil society;

- further development of inter-ethnic friendly relations in neighborhoods, improvement of effective mechanisms of preservation and development of language, culture, traditions and customs of representatives of different nationalities and peoples living in our republic;

- to further strengthen and develop the feeling of a multi-ethnic big family, friendship and harmony between representatives of different nationalities and peoples, to educate the young generation in the spirit of love and loyalty to the Motherland, to ensure equal rights of citizens;

- development of inter-ethnic friendly relations in neighborhoods, strengthening of friendly relations of multi-ethnic families in neighborhoods, support of compatriots and close cooperation with families married to representatives of Uzbeks and other nationalities abroad; - improving the organizational and legal foundations of inter-ethnic relations, taking into account the priority goals of developing inter-ethnic friendly relations in neighborhoods, advanced foreign experience.

In 2017, the 25th anniversary of the establishment of the Republic was widely celebrated at the International Cultural Center. In his speech at the meeting, the President of the center dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the international culture of the Republic, Shavkat Mirziyoev, evaluated the activity of the center and said: "It is noteworthy that the center of the international culture of the Republic coordinates the activities of national cultural centers, provides practical and methodological support. On the basis of bright events held in all regions of the country, the Center enriches our cultural and social life, strengthens the bonds of friendship and tolerance between people of different nationalities and ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan. It is worth noting that among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), only Uzbekistan has created such a structure". Today, 138 national-cultural centers in the country operate effectively as non-governmental non-profit organizations.

Another positive aspect of the development of inter-ethnic relations is the creation of an appropriate educational system in the country for the national composition of the population. Note that today there are 845 schools in the country teaching in Russian, 491 in Kazakh, 259 in Tajik, 52 in Turkmen, 40 in Kyrgyz and 7 in Korean. In addition to teachers, the pedagogical institutes under the Ministry of Uzbek language and literature prepare teachers for Russian, Tajik schools, Turkmen, Kazakh and Karakalpak languages.

The national content of the country's mass media meeting various needs is published in 8 languages: Uzbek, Karakalpak, Russian, Kazakh, Tajik, Turkmen, English and Korean. Television and radio in 12 languages (Uzbek, Karakalpak, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Tajik, Turkmen, Azerbaijani, Russian, Tatar, Bashkortostan, Korean, Uighur). Uzbekistan's international state policy is clearly based on humanity and democracy.

Uzbekistan has a unique experience in establishing inter-ethnic relations. It not only adheres to the principle of understanding national identity, nurturing a sense of national pride, preserving the language, culture and traditions of the Nations, as well as achieving the common unity of all the nations of the country. It should not be forgotten that where the importance of the idea is not understood, interethnic harmony, various things appear in the life of society, contradictions and problems that threaten peace and stability. Today's national conflicts in some countries of the world testify to this.

In the years of independence, one of the priorities of the state's policy was to ensure inter-ethnic harmony in society, to strengthen the environment of friendship and multi-ethnic family, to educate young people with love and loyalty to the Motherland, of national and universal importance. Today, representatives of more than 130 nationalities and ethnic groups, residents of the country using equal rights and opportunities, enshrined in the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, are effective in various sectors of the economy and social sphere, science and culture. They make a worthy contribution to the prosperity and strengthening of the country's independence.

Analyzing the large-scale democratic reforms, further liberalization of the political, economic, social and cultural spheres, as well as the implementation of important creative works

in other spheres of life, societies demonstrate the unification of representatives of all nationalities and ethnic groups living in Uzbekistan for a common purpose, such as the new Building a bright future for Uzbekistan.

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